

TACTICAL RULES FOR INVESTIGATING CRIMES COMMITTED BY WOMEN

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Abstract. *In this article the author thoroughly studied a number of versions of the fact that the crime was committed by a woman, as well as the main and additional investigative situations that may arise when it is clear that the criminal is a woman, special rules for investigation of crimes committed by a woman based on the general rules of planning, as well as this tactical rules that should be taken into account by the investigator during the investigation of crimes.*

Keywords: *tactic of investigation, version, typical situations, investigative planning, psychologist, interrogation.*

The main way to solve the problem situations that have arisen at the initial stage of the criminal investigation process is to correctly organize the versions of the investigation and thoroughly check them.

There are several definitions of criminalistic versions in the criminology literature. The main reason for this is that criminalistic versions are compiled and examined separately for each crime and its smallest details. For example, T.A. Abdumajidov describes the version as it is, the investigation version is the investigator's assumption about the nature and causes of the investigated event, the guilty persons and the nature of their guilt, other circumstances of the case. This means that data and evidence are summarized as widely as possible, their integration into a single isox; version is focused on solving the crime, exposing the criminals, and acquitting the innocent. Finally, the investigative version is an image, model, form of the investigated phenomena created in the imagination of the investigator. [1, p.216]

The investigative version must have the following features:

- ✓ be realistic and based on the study of evidence;
- ✓ does not contradict scientific data;
- ✓ logically structured and not having contradictions. [1, p.217].

In crimes committed by women, investigative versions have their own characteristics, where each investigative version is evaluated as an investigator's guess based on factual information about the crime under investigation.

We can see that in almost all criminalistics literature, in the investigation of crimes committed by women, there are no versions that can be put forward that the crime was committed by a woman. The main reason for this is that the very existence of the assumption that the crime was committed by a woman is the most common version of the crime put forward by the investigator. Therefore, in the process of investigating the crime, we propose to put forward additional versions based on the above version, depending on the circumstances of the case and the resulting investigation situation, and we consider it appropriate that the investigator should check the following versions based on the version that the crime was committed by a woman:

1. This crime was committed by an adult or minor woman;

2. The woman committed the crime intentionally or carelessly, or caused damage without fault due to circumstances beyond her control;
3. The woman committed the crime under certain pressure or due to financial or other coercion;
4. The woman did not understand the social consequences of her act during or before or after committing the crime due to her mental state;
5. The woman was a minor at the time of the crime;
6. The woman committed the crime as an accomplice;
7. The physiological and psychological state of a woman does not allow her to commit a crime or vice versa;
8. The woman admitted to committing the crime for the purpose of concealing the actions of other persons, etc.

In the investigation of crimes committed by women, the task of the investigator is not only to correctly determine the versions in a given situation, but also to develop the tactics of their verification, which means that after the versions have been conducted and the issues to be clarified have been determined, the investigator will find the evidence that confirms or rejects this or that version. determines what investigative actions and in what sequence they will be carried out. This sequence is directly related to investigative situations in the process of investigating crimes.

Criminological theory of investigative situations in the works of R. S. Belkin, I. F. Gerasimov, L. Ya. Drapkin, N. A. Selivanov, N. P. Yablokov, O. Ya. Baev, V. P. Bakhin and other criminologists developed. In their works, it is emphasized that investigative situations reflect the situation at each moment of the investigation of any criminal cases, and therefore, the correct implementation of the situation analysis is one of the most important aspects of the organization of investigative activities. Based on this, it should be recognized that investigative situations in criminal cases consist of a set of situations that reveal the specific characteristics of the investigation of a particular crime [1, p.217].

According to E. V. Vologina, who analyzed the methodology of crimes committed by women in her scientific works, the version that is created and checked in crimes committed by women directly originates from the framework of investigative situations that occurred [4].

According to T.V.Papova, investigative situations in the general practice of crime investigation are divided into two types. These are: conflict investigation situations and non-conflict investigation situations. In many crimes committed by women, the detective is faced with conflicting investigative situations. In such investigative situations, the investigator should fully study the information about the criminal woman and not ignore a number of subjective factors. Within the framework of subjective factors, the investigator should study the woman's social origin, place in social life, profession-related characteristics, age, education level, as well as self-esteem, emotional and psychological state.

Based on the above points, he distinguishes the following typical situations in the investigation of crimes committed by women:

- Situations in which the crime was committed and it was known to the investigation that it was committed by a woman;
- Situations in which it is known to the investigation that the crime was committed with participation and one of its participants is a woman;

• Cases where it is known to the investigation that a crime has been committed, but it is not known who committed it [5].

These investigative situations directly include the following elements in the process of organizing the investigation:

- ✓ composition of criminal actions (time, place, method, etc.);
- ✓ consequences of the committed crime;
- ✓ available general and personal information about the person who committed the crime;
- ✓ investigative situations related to the subject of the crime, for example, whether the stolen thing was found or not, whether the property was damaged, damaged or destroyed, and other situations;
- ✓ the time that passed from the time of the crime to the time when the information about the criminal event became known;
- ✓ circumstances related to the completeness, reliability and relevance of preliminary information on a criminal incident.

Until now, most researchers have paid special attention to investigative situations and emphasized that it is somewhat effective to organize an investigation based on investigative situations.

We can say that during the investigation of crimes committed by women and crimes committed by men, the investigator encounters slightly different investigative situations. In our opinion, the following are the most basic investigative situations that can arise in almost all types of crimes that can be committed by women:

1) the conditions observed at the scene of the crime and the presence of traces or information about it, which can often be left by a woman on material objects. In the case of such an investigation, the investigator can verify the version that the crime was committed by a woman by examining hair strands, lip or other cosmetic paints, items usually used by women or their parts, fibers or oils, fingerprints or footprints found during the inspection of the crime scene;

2) a case where the victim and witnesses testify that the crime was committed by a woman. Such a situation is relatively simple and acceptable for investigation. In this case, the investigator should check the instructions and for this purpose, he should appoint forensic experts, question the victim and witnesses;

3) cases where a woman suspected of committing a crime was caught directly at the scene of the crime or when she applied to the internal affairs office with a plea to confess her guilt. Such situations are rare in practice. Female criminals often try to hide their crimes for fear of being exposed in front of the community, based on the mentality of our society.

4) a situation where a woman suspected of committing a crime denies her guilt, but the investigator has some evidence that proves the woman's involvement in the crime. In this case, the investigator should conduct a repeated questioning. In this case, it will work well to show the woman who committed the crime the evidence that proves her guilt. Also, the female investigator may conduct interviews with witnesses and victims who provide accurate testimony, verify testimony at the scene of the incident, and conduct investigative experiments in order to uncover false testimony. If the investigation reveals that several women participated in the commission of the crime, and they deny their guilt despite the available evidence, the investigator should make sure that they do not see each other and do not communicate with each other. Also, their defenders can provide information, which leads to the agreement of further instructions. The collusion of the

accused complicates the investigation by concealing the truth. Therefore, all the accused should be investigated simultaneously or continuously (without breaks). This situation is very complicated and the success of the investigation in this case depends on the professionalism of the investigator and the high level of all investigative actions.

According to Russian scientists A.G. Phillipov and N.A. Burnashev, investigative situations do not depend on the persons who committed the crime, but rather on the specific type of crime committed [6].

But in the case where it is clear that the criminal is a woman, the following investigative situations may arise as an additional:

1. A situation where the victim or witnesses have not clearly seen the face of the criminal, but based on his behavior or actions, they can make an assumption that the suspect (or the accused) is a woman; for example, external signs related to the height and behavior of the person who committed the crime can sometimes be remembered by crime victims or bystanders and reported to the investigation.

2. Signs, traces and other information of the place where the crime was committed indicate that the crime was committed by a woman; for example, a strand of hair, lipstick, women's clothing or a specific piece thereof, and other items commonly used by women and the marks they leave behind.

3. The case where the victim and witnesses know the accused and know that he is a woman. According to psychological researchers who have studied the crimes committed by women according to the psychological characteristics of women, female criminals are more likely to make the victims of their crimes the people they know well. This situation will definitely help the investigator in clarifying the facts that are important for the case. In our opinion, the investigator should carry out the following investigative actions based on the above-mentioned investigative situations and check the versions he guessed based on the circumstances of the case:

questioning the victim (asking if there are any traces of injury on the accused himself or on his clothes);

conducting a search for traces and searching for places where minors may live;

identification and questioning of witnesses;

preparing a subjective portrait of the criminal for the purpose of gathering information;

assign special tasks to operative search officers regarding the place of the crime and the area where the criminal may live;

go back to the scene with the victim and re-examine it.

Investigating criminal cases is a complex process. Because the evidence proving the guilt or innocence of the persons who committed the crime, which is the most important in the criminal case, is obtained by conducting investigative actions. What kind of investigative action is appropriate depends to a large extent on the circumstances of the investigation and the examination of the allegations put forward according to the case. However, in order to verify the versions that the investigator is predicting in the investigation situation, he must properly organize the investigation and achieve certain results. Therefore, it is advisable to plan the investigation activities before starting the investigation.

Planning is a means of presenting evidence in a purposeful manner, and serves as the basis for organizing and directing the investigation. It includes accurate and timely identification of any investigative situation, creation of versions, development of ways and methods of their

investigation, as well as maximum use of scientific and technical tools and tactical methods in solving crimes. Planning determines what investigative actions should be conducted to determine the truth about the case, what sequence of tactical operations should be conducted to expose the behavior of a deaf criminal, and to conduct a complete and objective investigation. Various law enforcement agencies are involved in the investigation of crimes. Therefore, investigative planning is considered a factor that ensures the effectiveness of investigative work.

Speaking about the planning of the investigation, A. Kulakhmetov emphasized that the investigator should prepare a calendar plan, a special plan for the investigation of each criminal case and the conduct of each investigative action in order to conduct the investigation quickly, objectively and comprehensively [7].

All activities of the investigator related to the investigation are included in the calendar plan. It should include opening and investigating the crime, identifying the causes and consequences of the crime and eliminating them, carrying out legal propaganda, improving investigative skills.

N.P. Yablokov describes the plan of investigation of crimes belonging to this category as follows: “The investigation plan of the analyzed crimes will depend on the preliminary investigation situations, preliminary information and whether the criminal has been caught or not. At the same time, the plan should reflect all the circumstances that need to be proven. In the first phase, the investigation plan should focus on investigating the special versions as well as the regular versions. It is appropriate to include in the plan the necessary tactical operations for the considered cases” [3].

In the criminology literature, there is no information at all about what exactly it is possible to draw up an investigator’s calendar plan in the investigation of crimes committed by women. Therefore, we suggest that, based on the general rules of planning, in a crime case known to have been committed by a woman, the investigator should plan the investigation taking into account the following:

- When a plan is drawn up by an investigator for a crime committed by a woman, the psychology and personality characteristics of this subject should be reflected both in the general plan of investigation and in the plan of carrying out specific investigative actions. The reason is that women are psychologically different from men, some categories of women have a highly developed persuasive ability, and there are cases in which some of them try to distract the investigation by arousing pity in the investigator.

- In addition to the investigative activities carried out based on the nature of the investigation, it is necessary to include in the plan measures aimed at the investigator having complete information about the suspect or the accused.

- In addition, the investigator may include in the plan the implementation of measures to interrogate and obtain descriptions of persons from whom information can be obtained.

- In order to fully solve the crime and determine its causes, the investigator should plan to cooperate with the precinct inspectors serving in this area. The main reason for this is that in this case, the investigator has the opportunity to collect additional information important for the case about the position of the woman in the family and the neighborhood, the usual way of life, including the general environment in her home, disputes with family members, quarrels, etc.

One of the main issues of criminalistics is to ensure the practical activity of law enforcement agencies in the investigation of crimes committed by women in a special methodical and tactical manner.

In order to determine the truth and verify the evidence, various investigative actions are carried out, the main rules of which are defined in the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The tactical rules and general methodology for the implementation of these investigative actions are clearly described in the literature on criminalistics.

Statistical study of crimes committed by women during the practice, investigative activities of special importance in the investigation of crimes committed by women, such as inspection of the scene, interrogation, investigative experiment, forensic examination and search.

Inspection of the crime scene is one of the most basic preliminary investigative actions, regardless of who the subject of the crime is.

During the investigation of any crimes committed by women, examining the crime scene helps to understand whether the crime was committed by a woman and, if so, what her goals, interests, and habits are. Traces, objects left at the scene of the crime and the involvement of another person who may be an accomplice of the woman in the crime allow to determine whether or not.

Interrogating a suspect or accused woman. According to E.I. Elfimova and A.B. Solovyov, if the subject of the crime is a woman, the investigator should first establish psychological contact with the woman and gain her emotional trust. Therefore, we recommend that the investigator conducting the investigation should follow the following tactical rules during the interrogation of the female criminal:

Firstly, creating a comfortable environment for the interrogated woman during the interrogation is done by achieving this psychological contact. In this case, the interrogated woman should be able to see in the investigator a person who trusts her and understands her directly, who listens carefully to her every word.

Secondly, before starting the interrogation, the investigator should study the individual characteristics of the woman and prepare her psychologically and emotionally for the interrogation.

Thirdly, the investigator should prepare in advance the questions to be asked during the interrogation, and he should pay attention to the following: the mood, personal interests, habits and, most importantly, health of the woman being questioned; place in the family and society, work and education, specialization, education; age; religion; interaction with relatives and acquaintances; physiological and psychological state; first or repeated crime, previous conviction; participation in the crime as an organizer, executor, assistant or agent.

Fourthly, if the interrogated woman does not want to have a sincere dialogue with the investigator, and this situation is evident from her general answers to the questions during the interrogation, the investigator should invite a psychologist to the interrogation process. But in practice, there are many problems in ensuring the psychologist's participation in the interrogation process, including the fact that the psychologist's service is definitely paid, in this case, the problem of expenses arises by itself, and until the financial problem is solved, the investigation has to be postponed. As a result: distrust of the interrogator towards the investigator increases; delaying the questioning by the investigator reduces the possibility of achieving the expected result; the investigator deviates from the initial investigation plan; untimely results of interrogation postpone

the execution of further investigative actions; most importantly, it risks violating the procedural rules related to the general investigation period.

We suggest taking the following measures to eliminate these problems related to the participation of a psychologist or pedagogue not only in the process of interrogation and investigation, but also in the process of search and confrontation (For example, according to Article 228.1 of the Criminal Procedure Code of Azerbaijan, Article 197 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Kyrgyz Republic, and Article 218 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the rules on the participation of a psychologist in the conduct of a face-to-face investigation are established), especially if the subject of the crime is a woman or a minor:

Organization of psychologist staff in investigative bodies. In this case, it is necessary to procedurally determine the processes that arise due to the introduction of this staff, the development of their specific tasks and functions, the issue of their working hours and salaries, and other labor relations.

Special training courses on human psychology should be organized so that the employees who carry out direct inquiry and preliminary investigation can learn more about human psychology and use it effectively in investigative practice. In these training courses, the psychology of women and minors should be studied in depth by investigators. (A number of training courses in this regard have been introduced in the Russian Federation).

In today's politics, it is directly related to strengthening the legal status of women (women) in the management of society and state affairs, creating new opportunities to increase their legal consciousness and legal culture in this regard, as well as loans and subsidies in business activities, the goal of introducing additional benefits in terms of increasing the number of quotas in the educational process and determining jobs is defined as one of the most important directions in the development strategy of our country. Based on the wide range of opportunities available to women, we suggest that women's interrogation should be carried out by more **female investigators** according to the distribution of investigations, given the complexity of women's psychology.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men", taking into account that special emphasis is placed on the issue of ensuring equal participation of women and men in the competition for holding positions in the public service, including leadership positions, on the issues of increasing the number of qualified female(women) personnel in law enforcement agencies, including pre-investigation, inquiry, investigation and judicial bodies, further strengthening the system of women's support and their position in society is in accordance with the reforms carried out by the president of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoyev and it will have an effective impact on the future of New Uzbekistan.

In practice, women often change their testimony against men, and in some cases, they completely forget their answers during the preliminary interrogation or they slander the investigation by saying that they gave their testimony under the influence of illness, insanity, excitement or, most often, under the pressure of the investigator, and there are many cases of misleading the investigation. In order to avoid such misunderstandings during the interrogation process, we recommend that the use of video recording during the interrogation process (as well as during other investigative actions) should be made mandatory. Recording each investigation on videotape or disk increases the effectiveness and reliability of the investigation.

"Auxiliary methods in recording evidence" of the Code of Criminal Procedure. We suggest adding the following 8 points to Article 91, known as "Appendices to the Protocol".

The following procedural actions must be recorded by video recording:

- 1) inspecting the scene of an incident in the case of serious crimes;
- 2) search;
- 3) checking the reports at the scene of the incident;
- 4) investigative experiment;
- 5) arresting a person;
- 6) waiver of the defender;
- 7) personal search and seizure carried out during the arrest of a person;

8) questioning (if this proposal is appropriate, it is necessary to amend the relevant articles of the Criminal Procedure Code, which determine the general rules of interrogation) (for example, on March 10, 2021, the Kyrgyz Criminal Procedure Code noted the cases of using audio and video recordings during interrogation under Article 193).

Many guarantees are established for women in our legislation, including, in connection with the declaration of 1999 as “Women’s Year”, according to the Law “On Additional Benefits for Women” dated April 14 of the same year, According to Articles 116 and 228 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, women who have children under the age of three and work in institutions and organizations financially supported by the budget, working hours of no more than 35 hours per week have been introduced, and they are guaranteed full-time wages; according to articles 119 and 229, at the request of a pregnant woman, a woman with a child under the age of fourteen (a disabled child under the age of sixteen), including a woman who has such a child under her care, or a person who is busy caring for a sick member of the family, the employer in accordance with the conclusion, they are guaranteed to be assigned a part-time working day or a part-time working week; In part 1 of Article 236, women with children under the age of two are given additional breaks for feeding the child, in addition to breaks for rest and meals. These breaks are given at least once every three hours with a duration of not less than thirty minutes each. If there are two or more children under the age of two, the duration of the break is at least one hour.

In our opinion, within the framework of the above-mentioned guarantees, based on the norms of the labor law, Article 107 of the Civil Code applies to women of this category, pregnant women, women with children under 2 years of age, and a woman with a child under the age of fourteen (a disabled child under the age of sixteen), including , we suggest that the questioning time of a woman with such a child or a person who is busy caring for a sick member of the family should be set to 6 hours according to their family conditions and physiological condition, and additional breaks should be given for feeding the child. According to it, Article 107 of the Criminal Procedure Code should be supplemented with the following clauses:

“Interrogation of pregnant women, women with children under the age of two, and women with children under the age of fourteen (disabled children under the age of sixteen), including a woman who has such a child under her patronage or a person engaged in caring for a sick member of the family, should not exceed six hours.

Women with children under two years of age and women with children under the age of fourteen (disabled children under the age of sixteen), including women who have such a child under their patronage or persons engaged in caring for a sick member of the family, to feed the child or a sick member of the family, and pregnant women taking into account their pregnancy, additional breaks are also given. These breaks shall be given at least once every three hours, with a duration of not less than thirty minutes each”.

This proposal does not directly cause protests in terms of gender equality between women and men, because:

Firstly, the above clauses are in accordance with the Law "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" adopted on August 17, 2019, and the implementation of strategies and programs in the health sector that take into account the various needs of women with Article 27 of the law. It is included among the guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men in the field of health.

Secondly, pregnancy and feeding (breastfeeding) a child up to two years of age is a natural condition that belongs only to women, and the fact that men are not capable of it from a biological point of view, it is inappropriate to raise the issue of gender equality in this regard.

Thirdly, a woman with a child under the age of fourteen (disabled child under the age of sixteen), including a woman who has such a child under her care or a person who is busy caring for a sick member of the family, means not only women, but also men, that is, there is no limit.

Fourthly, the clause does not mention all women (women), that is, women who are distinguished by physiological and biological aspects are meant.

Article 187 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Russian Federation states: "If there are medical instructions, the period of interrogation is determined based on the conclusion of the doctor, and this practice is effectively used in the Russian procedural system. This norm is also mentioned in Article 190 of the Criminal Code of the Kyrgyz Republic. Article 209 of the Republic of Kazakhstan, known as the place, time and duration of interrogation, also defines the rule of determining the time of interrogation based on a medical opinion, in paragraph 3-1 of this article:

- 1) women who are pregnant or have young children;
- 2) women aged fifty-eight and older;
- 3) it is noted that the time of continuous questioning of men aged sixty and older should not exceed 3 hours, and the total duration of questioning should not exceed five hours.

In paragraph 4 of this article, the questioning of a minor shall be carried out during the day and without breaks of more than two hours, in general, for a period of no more than four hours. If it is clear that the minor is exhausted, it is noted that the interrogation will be stopped before this period has passed.

It should be mentioned that the addition of Article 107 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan with a clause of this content, as a logical continuation of the above-recommended clauses, on the one hand, makes the clauses more meaningful, and also solves the issue of gender equality.

Types of expertise assigned in crimes committed against women. In the investigation of crimes committed by women, the investigator more often appoints the following expertise:

a) Forensic psychiatric examination. Information about the mental state of a woman who is suspected (or accused) of a crime is obtained based on the conclusion of this expert. This is to check his sanity and determine whether he has any mental defects or defects;

b) Forensic - psychological examination. This expertise answers questions such as the mental development of the woman who committed the crime, if she is mentally retarded, whether she understood her actions at the time of committing the crime, whether she was able to control them, and whether she could give clear instructions.

c) Human DNA forensic biological examination. In many crimes committed by women, a lot of biological materials (blood, sperm, saliva, hair fibers) are detected. In order to clarify that they

really belong to a woman, the investigator must appoint this type of examination and ask the expert the following preliminary general questions:

- Are the biological materials submitted for expert examination suitable for expert examination?

- From what gender did the biological material, for example, hair strands, blood, skin stains come from?

- Biological materials are actually A. descended from a woman named?

- Is the biological material submitted from one woman or from several?

d) Scientific (trasological) expertise. The most important sign that encourages the version that the crime was committed by a woman is the trasological traces found at the crime scene. Female criminals often leave fingerprints and shoe prints at crime scenes. That's why the investigator appoints a dactyloscopic examination as one of the types of trasological examination in such situations. For example, in the course of the investigation, the investigator identified a female suspect, T. At the time of committing the crime of theft, the victim D., who was his close relative. was found to have left fingerprints on the glass of an inexpensive wristwatch, and he took samples from it and submitted a dactyloscopic examination. The investigator asked the expert the following questions:

Are there fingerprints (palm) on the glass of the presented wristwatch?

- ✓ Are the fingerprints left on the provided wristwatch valid for identification?

- ✓ Are fingerprints captured on dactyloscopy film from a wristwatch valid for identification?

- ✓ If applicable, are they left by citizen T.

The act of investigation. In the investigation of crimes committed by women, in many cases, in order to verify the testimony given by them, if there are serious contradictions between the testimonies of the two persons who were previously questioned, a face-to-face investigation may be conducted between them. In practice, women do not show much desire for face-to-face investigation. They avoid face-to-face investigations for fear of being recognized or being exposed. Women are also afraid that they will retaliate against them in the future. But despite this, conducting this investigative action can be a decisive way to determine the truth in some cases. When conducting this investigation, the investigator or prosecutor prepares separately and determines the objections from the previous interrogation report. It is suggested to explain each conflict to both persons in turn during the investigation process.

Inspection of reports at the scene of the incident. According to E.I. Elfimova, according to statistics, half of the women who committed crimes give false testimony during the initial interrogation. In view of this, in the investigation of crimes committed by women, in most cases, the investigators conduct an investigation by examining the evidence at the scene of the incident. Because this investigative act serves as a "lie detection indicator" that determines the truth of the testimony given by female criminals [2, p.192].

According to surveys conducted in the course of the practice, the investigation of the evidence at the scene of the incident is more often carried out in the case of crimes committed by women than in other investigations. The main reason for this is that the investigator will get new information about the case through this investigative action, and will also have the opportunity to determine whether the initial statements of the suspect (or accused) are true or false. Also, the testimony of the examination of the evidence at the scene of the incident increases the possibility

of the investigated suspect (or accused) to relive the criminal incident in memory and to give additional testimony about small details important for the investigation.

In her scientific work, E.I. Elfimova emphasizes that the investigator should have a special approach to the implementation of this investigative action, and mentions the following tactical rules that give an effective result in conducting this investigative action:

- Before the investigator goes to the scene of the incident, he must thoroughly interrogate the suspect (or accused) woman, whose testimony is being checked, about every situation related to the crime scene;
- Having independent additional information about the place where the incident took place;
- Formation of the environment at the time of the crime at the scene of the incident;
- It is necessary to correctly choose the time of investigation, if the crime was committed during the day, during the day, otherwise, in the evening.
- To conduct this investigative action, it is necessary to form the composition of the participants, to ensure that no other persons are present at the scene of the incident.
- He should also prepare the necessary technical means. [2, p.195]

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